

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINING THE 2D SHAPE OF AN OBJECT WITH A MICROCONTROLLER

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Abstract

The article focuses on 2d identification of objects and image capture using software.

Keywords: ultrasonic, figure, digital, object, interval.

Ultrasound technology has been used for years. The aim of this work is to build an ultrasonic device based on trigonometric rules, which is basically a kind of radar system, to obtain the exact distance and approximate 2D form for fixed objects placed around the device. It uses the distance of an ultrasonic sensor with trigonometric rules to get the shape of the object. We can even use this technique to create a map of an area. Sonars can have three different purposes :

1. Obstruction Prevention: The first detected echo measures the range of the nearest object. Robots use this information to plan paths around obstacles and avoid collisions.

2. Sonar mapping: A set of echoes is used to create a map of the environment.

3. Object Recognition: A sequence of echo or sonar maps is developed to classify physical objects. These are mainly a combination of different surfaces.

It is necessary to use two ultrasonic sensors to show the two-dimensional shape of the object. One ultrasound sensor will move in the XZ plane (horizontal motion) and the other ultrasonic sensor will move in the XY plane (vertical motion). When moving in the XZ plane, the ultrasound sensor will provide the shape of the object around the X axis. It will determine the direction of the object along the X axis ($x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots x_n$) and the direction along the y axis ($y_1, y_2, y_3 \dots y_n$). The ultrasound sensor will give the distance to the object. Because the transmitter and receiver are close to each other, the transmitted wavelength has the same value as the received wavelength.

Fig. 1. The logical scheme of the device

The microcontroller is a highly integrated chip that combines all the components. This includes the CPU, RAM, some kind of ROM, input / output ports and timers. The ultrasonic sensor determines the distance to the arduino by analyzing the information coming from the sensors. Only four angles are used here. Two angles were used to control the servos and two angles were used to control the ultrasound sensors. The system is designed so that if a sensor or servo does not work, the

overall system will not work or start. If the transmitted and received waves coincide, the expected results will not be achieved. Thus, the transducer was given a sufficient delay to determine the measurement in each cycle. Here, the full rotation for each sensor was calculated starting at 45 degrees, reached 165 degrees and returned to its previous state. Distances and angle values from the Arduino were sent by creating an array of the system.

Fig. 2. The working form of the algorithm

Once the Arduino is connected to the computer and powered on, the angular values of the x and y values will be displayed on the serial monitor. The values

displayed on this series monitor can be used to verify that the microcontroller and components are working.

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COM19 (Arduino/Genuino Uno)
Distance in cm for y: 5
x(in cm) =0 y(in cm) =-2 Angle up and down: 140 , Angle right to left: 45 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 6
x(in cm) =0 y(in cm) =-5 Angle up and down: 135 , Angle right to left: 45 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 6
x(in cm) =0 y(in cm) =0 Angle up and down: 130 , Angle right to left: 45 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 7
x(in cm) =0 y(in cm) =-6 Angle up and down: 125 , Angle right to left: 45 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 7
x(in cm) =0 y(in cm) =-4 Angle up and down: 120 , Angle left to right: 55 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 7
x(in cm)=0 y(in cm)=4 Angle up and down: 125 , Angle left to right: 55 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 9
x(in cm)=0 y(in cm)=-5 Angle up and down: 130 , Angle left to right: 55 , Distance in cm:
Distance in cm for y: 8
x(in cm)=0 y(in cm)=7 Angle up and down: 135 , Angle left to right: 55 , Distance in cm:

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Fig. 3. Finally, the results we get on a serial monitor.

The system is connected as shown in Figure 2. The information obtained is presented in two different forms. One is displayed on the serial monitor of the screen, and the other is displayed in MATLAB by drawing a graph. The output of the object can be better displayed using software. To start the system, the system was tested by transmitting to MATLAB only the distance with the serial port. The final result shows that we have obtained the correct result by comparing the graphical values with the mathematical values. The final test phase was tested by measuring the distance. The serial monitor is always kept open to check the operation of the system while the device is running.

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